

1 **Title**

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3 Bark beetles as microclimate engineers – thermal characteristics of infested spruce trees at the
4 canopy surface and below the canopy

5

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25

26 Abstract

27

28 Over recent decades, Spruce bark beetle outbreaks have expanded and intensified across Europe,
29 driven by a warming climate and more frequent extreme drought events. While research has largely
30 focused on early detection and vulnerability prediction, little is known about the consequences of
31 beetle infestations on forest microclimates. Bark beetle attacks are expected to alter forest
32 microclimates due to changes in canopy cover, albedo, wind patterns, and evapotranspiration. We
33 explored the effect of bark beetle attacks on summer forest microclimate using two approaches.

34 Firstly, we measured understory microclimate at 2-m height in 31 Swedish forest stands using small
35 consumer-grade loggers. Along a gradient of attack severity, represented by increasing proportions
36 of dead spruces, maximum summer day-time temperatures increased by up to 2 °C, with this
37 warming effect being moderated by the presence of deciduous broadleaf trees. Surprisingly, night-
38 time minimum temperatures were not affected by bark beetle attacks.

39 Secondly, we mapped canopy surface temperature over one part of the study area using
40 multispectral and thermal drone imaging, contrasting canopy temperatures of healthy and infested
41 trees. We observed that dead trees were generally warmer than living trees, by an average of 2.6 °C
42 on a sunny day and 0.7 °C on a cloudy day.

43 Our study documented changes in thermal regimes in both the understory and overstory after bark
44 beetle attacks, indicating that climate-change related disturbances are fuelling rapid increases in
45 microclimate warming. However, even dead forest stands may function as thermal buffers for
46 understory vegetation, as we found minimum temperatures being unaffected by bark beetles.
47 Finally, our results suggest that increasing the proportion of deciduous trees can decrease the risk of
48 bark-beetle induced microclimate warming. The insights gained can guide forest succession and
49 regeneration management after disturbances, contributing to critical decisions on conservation
50 areas and salvage logging strategies.

51

52 Keywords

53

54 forest disturbance, UAV, remote sensing, thermal infrared imagery, forest management, *in situ*
55 sensors, *Ips typographus*

1. Introduction

57 Forest canopies play a crucial role in moderating local microclimates by buffering temperature
58 extremes and mitigating macroclimate warming. Forest microclimate buffering is an important
59 ecosystem function supporting biodiversity and forest resilience to climate change (De Frenne et al.,
60 2021). For example, cool and buffered microclimates support the local survival of range-edge
61 populations of cold-adapted species that are threatened by a warming climate (Greiser et al., 2020,
62 Finocchiaro et al., 2024). Near forest edges, where microclimate buffering declines, forest
63 understory species are more negatively affected by drought (Koelemeijer et al., 2023). And
64 bryophytes as well as vascular plants classified as forest-core specialists have a strong affinity to
65 forest microclimate buffering (Gril, et al., 2024). However, forest buffering capacity is being altered
66 by large-scale disturbances, many of which are intensifying due to climate change.

67 Among the most significant of these disturbances in Europe's coniferous forests are outbreaks of the
68 European spruce bark beetle (*Ips typographus* L.), referred to hereafter as the bark beetle. This
69 species targets primarily Norway spruce trees (*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.). In recent years, attacks of the
70 bark beetle have increased in both intensity and area, driven by drier and warmer summers
71 (Netherer et al., 2024). As an ectothermic insect, the bark beetle benefits from longer and warmer
72 growing seasons, which accelerate its development and enable multiple generations per year
73 (Jakoby et al., 2019). At the same time, drought-stressed spruce trees become more vulnerable as
74 their weakened defences cannot withstand beetle attacks (Huang et al., 2020). Additionally, the
75 prevalence of spruce monocultures, a product of past and current forestry practices, increases the
76 forest's vulnerability to these outbreaks. Between 2002 and 2010, an average of 14.5 million m³ of
77 timber was damaged annually in Europe by bark beetle infestations (Seidl et al., 2011), contributing
78 to rising large-scale canopy mortality (Senf et al., 2018). The European spruce bark beetle is
79 therefore recognized as the most economically destructive insect pest in Europe's coniferous forests
80 (Biedermann et al., 2019), while also being an ecologically important keystone species (Huang et al.,
81 2020).

82 Bark beetle attacks harm trees in two main ways. First, the beetle tunnels in the inner bark disrupt
83 the vascular system, impeding water and nutrient transport. Second, the beetle transmits a blue wilt
84 fungus (*Ophiostoma* spp.), which colonizes the tree's tissues, further blocking the flow of water and
85 nutrients. The fungal growth accelerates the tree's decline by causing dehydration and reducing its
86 ability to mount defences (Huo et al., 2021). In case of intensive infestation, trees start to drop green
87 needles (green stage), followed by needle browning (red stage), progressive twig loss and bark
88 shedding (gray stage). This process of tree mortality, the succession from the green via the red to the
89 final gray stage can take several years (Siegert et al. 2024).

90 When trees die, the forest ecosystem undergoes drastic transformations. Bark beetles are thus
91 considered ecosystem engineers, capable of altering the forest's light, moisture and temperature
92 dynamics (Bright et al., 2013), surface water chemistry (Kopáček et al., 2017) and understory
93 communities (Davis et al., 2020; Bouget and Duelli, 2004; Lehnert et al., 2013). Their impact also
94 extends to the carbon balance of forests (Huang et al., 2020; see a full review of community and
95 biogeochemical effects in Siegert et al. 2024). Most of the ongoing research focuses on three key
96 areas: 1) early detection and mapping of infestations (Huo et al., 2021; Trubin et al., 2024;
97 Zakrzewska & Kopeć, 2022), 2) predisposition and risk analysis of attacks (Olsson et al., 2024; Huo et
98 al., 2024; Müller et al., 2022), and 3) the social and ecological consequences of outbreaks (Davis et
99 al., 2020, Hlásny et al., 2021). Relatively few studies have investigated the thermal changes in forest

100 canopies and understories following bark beetle attacks (but see e.g. Hais & Kučera, 2008; Bright et
101 al., 2013), despite a call for more studies on the direct and indirect impact of climate change on
102 forest microclimate buffering capacity (Lombaerde et al., 2022).

103 The forest understory microclimate is characterized by buffered temperature extremes, typically
104 resulting in cooler maximum temperatures and warmer minimum temperatures compared to open
105 areas (De Frenne et al., 2021; Geiger et al., 2012). This buffering effect is mainly a result of the
106 canopy blocking incoming and outgoing radiation, as well as latent heat fluxes such as evaporative
107 cooling during hot and dry summer days (Davis et al., 2019; Geiger et al., 2012; Greiser et al., 2024;
108 Von Arx et al., 2013).

109 Bark beetle infestations can change forest microclimate by altering the canopy and, consequently,
110 the thermal properties of both the canopy and the understory. As trees defoliate and the canopy
111 opens, more sunlight penetrates during the day leading to a warming effect on daily maximum
112 temperatures (T_{max}) (Royer et al., 2011). Conversely, at night, the open canopy allows more heat to
113 escape, cooling daily minimum temperatures (T_{min}). This results in larger temperature fluctuations
114 and reduced thermal buffering in the understory (Brůna et al., 2024; De Frenne et al., 2021).
115 Additionally, healthy, transpiring trees contribute to cooling the canopy surface and understory via
116 latent heat fluxes (Greiser et al., 2024; Pokorný, 2001; Von Arx et al., 2013). Attacked and dead trees
117 transpire significantly less water (Bright et al., 2013), which can amplify the warming of T_{max} in the
118 understory and at the canopy surface. On the other hand, the albedo of dying, defoliating and
119 debarking spruce trees may increase (Bright, et al., 2013), potentially leading to a cooling effect
120 during sunny days with high incoming direct solar radiation, though Chen et al. (2015) have found
121 this effect to be relatively small compared to the decreases in evapotranspiration and and increases
122 in sensible heat fluxes after bark beetle outbreaks. While the physics behind each process are well
123 known, the absolute thermal effects of bark beetle attacks on forest microclimate remain poorly
124 quantified at the forest stand level and require further investigation.

125 Relatively few studies exist that measure temperature *in situ* along an attack gradient or before and
126 after bark beetle attacks (but see e.g., Bílá et al., 2018, Morehouse et al., 2008, Brůna *et al.*, 2024).
127 One outstanding exception is the long-term study by Kopáček et al. (2020), who measured
128 microclimate and hydrological changes after bark-beetle induced tree dieback in mountain spruce
129 forest of central Europe. They detected increases in air temperature after tree dieback by 1.2 °C,
130 additionally to increases in soil temperature, soil moisture and run-off. Also, Morehouse et al. (2008)
131 found soil and air temperatures in the growing season to be higher in beetle-infested Ponderosa
132 pine stands compared to healthy stands.

133 In addition to *in situ* monitoring, remote sensing has emerged as a promising solution for forest
134 damage monitoring (Mngadi et al., 2024). A review study found 58 research papers published from
135 2003 to 2022 using remote sensing techniques to monitor bark beetle damage, including satellite
136 imagery, Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR), airborne and drone-based multispectral,
137 hyperspectral, and thermal imagery (Marvasti-Zadeh, et al., 2024). Among various types of remote
138 sensing techniques, thermal imagery has been the least investigated (3 out of the 58 papers in the
139 review), although it can be an efficient tool to analyze the thermal conditions of damaged forests. To
140 date, only a few bark beetle studies used satellite thermal imagery at the landscape level (e.g.,
141 Abdullah et al. 2019; Hais & Kučera et al., 2008; Bárta et al., 2022), or airborne thermal imagery at
142 the individual-tree level (e.g., Junttila et al., 2017; Zakrzewska et al., 2022) and the focus is often on
143 using thermal signatures for detection of attacks (Abdullah et al. 2019; Zakrzewska et al., 2022).
144 Abdullah et al. (2019) used thermal infrared images with 100 m resolution from Landsat-8 satellite
145 and found that attacked plots had higher canopy surface temperatures than healthy plots and that

146 the temperature differences between healthy and attacked plots increased later in the growing
147 season. Hais & Kučera et al. (2008) used Landsat thermal images (120 and 60 m resolution) to
148 calculate surface temperature calibrated by topography. When comparing the temperature changes
149 between 1987 and 2002, the temperature almost remained the same in areas with living spruce
150 forests ($\Delta T = 0.4$ °C), while the temperature increased by 3.5 °C in bark beetle infested forests. Using
151 MODIS satellite data, Maness et al. (2013) demonstrated that pine beetle outbreaks significantly
152 increased the summertime surface temperature by around 1 °C across 170,000 km² of affected
153 forest in Canada. Kozhoridze et al. (2023) used surface temperature data generated from Landsat
154 thermal bands to analyse susceptibility to bark beetle attacks and found that attacked canopies were
155 warmer already in a year prior to bark beetle infestations.

156 Junttila et al. (2017) acquired relative surface temperature of infested boreal forests in Southern
157 Finland from airborne thermal imagery with 1 m resolution, and found that severely defoliated
158 forests attacked by bark beetles had significantly higher temperatures than healthy ones. However,
159 the forest structure effect on the relative surface temperature dominated over the effect of
160 defoliation, which could be caused by the relatively cold and humid flight conditions during that day,
161 highlighting the importance of repeating UAV-flights under different weather conditions (Brown et
162 al., 2024). Zakrzewska et al. (2022) used a similar approach in temperate North-eastern Poland and
163 used crown surface temperature to classify healthy, infested, and dead trees. Using airborne thermal
164 imagery from a clear summer day with 29 °C air temperature, they found dead trees on average to
165 be 2.5 °C warmer than living trees, with average temperatures of healthy, discoloured and dead
166 trees being 27.7, 28.6, and 30.2 °C, respectively.

167 Drones, or Unoccupied Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), are highly flexible platforms for carrying sensors and
168 have demonstrated great potential for monitoring bark beetle damage using multispectral sensors
169 (Bozzini et al., 2025, Huo et al., 2023). Consequently, drone-based thermal imagery could be a
170 valuable tool for analysing temperature variations associated with forest damage, complementing
171 microclimate studies with *in-situ* measurements. Despite this potential, a recent review by Smigaj et
172 al. (2023) identified only eight publications that utilized UAV-based thermal imagery to monitor
173 stress responses in forests. Most studies have used canopy temperature changes as a proxy for tree
174 stress caused by drought or pathogens. In contrast, our study focuses on the direct temperature
175 response in and below forest canopies, particularly in relation to bark beetle infestations.

176 Most of the studies we reviewed have been conducted in temperate forests of Europe or in North
177 America, and have focused on either land/canopy surface temperatures or on sub-canopy air
178 temperatures. However, we miss studies that 1) quantify microclimate changes after bark beetle
179 attacks in the *boreal* forest (but see Junttila et al. 2017), 2) look at *both* overstory and understory
180 temperatures, 3) also consider *night-time* temperatures and 4) study the microclimate change under
181 different *weather* conditions. With our study, we would like to address all of these points.

182 Our aim was to quantify the change in summer canopy surface temperature and understory air
183 temperature in boreal forests after bark beetle attacks using *in-situ* microclimate loggers and UAV-
184 based thermal imagery (Fig. 1). We worked in a heterogeneous forest landscape with mixed forests
185 and mosaics of attacked and healthy trees and focused on changes during the warmest season but
186 considering different weather conditions.

187

188 We asked:

- 189 1) How does day and night time understory air temperature change along an attack severity
190 gradient (space-for-time substitution)?
- 191 2) What is the canopy surface temperature difference between bark beetle-killed and living
192 trees within the same stand?

193 To answer question 1), we used a network of microclimate loggers in 31 forest stands in 5 different
194 nature reserves in Southern Sweden. We explored, if and how much understory temperatures
195 during the growing season of 2021 changed along an attack severity gradient, and if the effect is
196 dependent on the proportion of deciduous broadleaf trees and weather conditions.

197 To answer question 2), we used UAV-based thermal imagery from one of the nature reserves and
198 two repeated flights under different weather conditions in the summer. We quantified the
199 temperature difference at the canopy surface between dead and living trees for each of the two
200 flights.

201

202 2. Materials and methods

203 2.1. Study area

204 The study was conducted in Södermanland, southern Sweden, at 58°N 17°E (Fig. 1b). Yearly mean air
205 temperature is 7 °C and the yearly precipitation is 400 – 600 mm (SMHI, 2024). The mean air
206 temperature of July and August in 2021 was 18 °C. The landscape is covered with a mosaic of forests,
207 farmlands and lakes. The forest at all sites was dominated by spruce. Other common species in the
208 study area were pine, birch, aspen and alder. Södermanland was in 2022 identified as one of the
209 “epicentres” in southern Sweden of spruce bark beetle attacks with approximately 16.2 m³ ha⁻¹
210 attacked volume of spruce (Wulff and Roberge, 2023). We selected five nature reserves (Ekeby,
211 Toregrav, Fräkenkärret, Noret and Storhultet), which experienced recent attacks by the spruce bark
212 beetle. In nature reserves, stands of bark beetle-attacked trees are left for free development
213 compared to managed forests, where attacked stands are usually salvage-logged (Swedish
214 Environmental Protection Agency, 2023). Attacks in the studied nature reserves were from 2018 or
215 later, i.e., 3 years or younger by the time of our study in 2021. The majority of attacked trees were in
216 the red or grey attack stage, but as attacks were spreading in some places, even green attack stages
217 were detected (Siegert et al., 2024). The selected reserves are at max. 25 km apart from each other
218 thus experiencing the same macroclimate and weather.

219 2.2. Logger site selection

220 For each reserve, we had spatial information on bark beetle attacks from the years 2018-2020
221 (Länsstyrelsen Södermanland). We focused on spruce-dominated stands with a minimum of 10 m³
222 ha⁻¹ standing volume of spruce. We established 31 logger sites across the five reserves covering
223 gradients of attack severity (proportion of dead spruce) and deciduousness (proportion of deciduous
224 trees such as aspen and birch, Fig. 2). About half of the sites were classified as completely healthy
225 during site selection. All sites were placed at least 100 m apart from each other and 40 m away from
226 the nearest forest edge, with the exception of one site (19B) that was 20 m close to a younger forest.
227 (See Supplementary Material, Appendix 1 for details on site selection, and Table S1 for a summary of
228 microclimate-relevant site features for all sites.)

229

230 *Fig. 1. a) Schematic overview of our two approaches to study b) understory temperature differences*
 231 *along an attack gradient, and c) canopy surface temperature differences between living and dead*
 232 *trees. The study area is situated in Södermanland county, Sweden (b), where we installed 31 loggers*
 233 *across five nature reserves. In one of the reserves (Ekeby), we also collected UAV-borne thermal*
 234 *imagery to estimate canopy surface temperature (c). The two core areas used for analyses of canopy*
 235 *surface temperature are delineated in blue in the orthophoto in panel b).*

236

237 2.3. Microclimate logger and weather data

238 At each plot, we measured understory air temperature with a TOMST Thermologger, installed at 2 m
239 height at the north side of a tree, and protected with a white inverted plastic garden pot blocking
240 direct sunlight and rain (Fig. S2). Loggers were installed between 17 May and 28 June 2021 and
241 downloaded between 22 and 27 September 2021. We used data from the summer period (1st July –
242 21st September 2021). Temperature was recorded every 15 minutes with an accuracy of ± 0.5 °C.
243 The raw data was cleaned, merged and aggregated using the package *myClim* (Man et al., 2023). We
244 aggregated the temperature data to daily minimum and maximum temperatures for each site,
245 hereafter called minimum and maximum temperature (*Tmin*, *Tmax*) respectively (Fig. 2). Due to a
246 consistent diurnal temperature cycle, maximum temperatures coincided with day-time temperature
247 and minimum temperatures coincided with night-time temperature. We further aggregated data to
248 summer averages of daily minimum and maximum temperatures. As a response in our models, we
249 used summer-averaged temperatures and temperatures of one single cloudy and one single clear
250 day. Daily average cloud cover estimates for all plots were obtained from the nearest weather
251 station in Floda (59.055°N, 16.3944°E, smhi.se).

252
253 *Fig. 2. Distribution of summer-averaged daily understory maximum and minimum temperature,*
254 *elevation, proportion of dead spruce trees, proportion of deciduous trees and canopy openness of 31*
255 *microclimate logger sites, obtained during the growing season 2021. Proportion of dead and*
256 *deciduous trees is based on on-site basal area measurements. See Table S1 for site-specific features.*

257

258 2.4. Environmental data from the logger sites

259 At each site, we took a hemispheric canopy image generated from a 360° photosphere taken at ca.
260 1.5 m height. The photospheres were taken with a standard Android smartphone and the app
261 Google Street View© and transformed into 180° hemispheric images with the software
262 ImageMagick v.7.0.10 using the workflow presented by Arietta (2022). The gap fraction was
263 calculated from binarized images using the software ImageJ 1.53 and the Hemispherical_2.0 plugin
264 (Beckschäfer, 2015). Gap fraction is a measurement of canopy openness in the form of the
265 proportion of sky pixels in a binarized image, and is closely related to the amount of light that
266 reaches the forest floor.

267 During the revisit in September, we recorded the standing basal area [$\text{m}^2 \text{ha}^{-1}$] per tree species with
268 a standard relascope at each logger plot. Based on these basal area estimates, we calculated total
269 basal area (a measure for forest density), proportion of dead spruce and proportion of deciduous
270 trees (Fig. 2).

271 2.5. UAV data

272 Multispectral and thermal images were acquired using a MicaSense Series Altum sensor mounted on
273 a DJI Matrice 200 Series V2 drone. The Altum sensor synchronized high-resolution RGB, thermal, and
274 multispectral data, including a thermal sensor at 7.5 -13.5 μm , and multispectral sensor at Blue (475
275 nm centre, 32 nm bandwidth), Green (560 nm centre, 27 nm bandwidth), Red (668 nm centre, 14
276 nm bandwidth), Red Edge (717 nm centre, 12 nm bandwidth), and Near-IR (842 nm centre, 57 nm
277 bandwidth) bands. Images were collected at 120 m above ground with 80% side and front overlap,
278 resulting in a Ground Sample Distance (GSD) of 5.28 cm for the multispectral images and 33.5 cm for
279 the thermal images. In order to show the potential effect of sunny and cloudy days on crown surface
280 temperature, images were collected in clear sky conditions on 21 July 2021 and under a fully
281 overcast sky on 31 July 2021. Weather conditions during the flights were extracted from the nearby
282 Floda weather station (see above paragraph 2.3.). The flight mission on July 21 took place between
283 11:38 and 13:02 local time with an average free air temperature of 21.2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity of 35%,
284 wind speed of 2.1 m/s and 0% cloud cover. On July 31, the flight mission was executed between 9:32
285 and 11:06 local time with an average free air temperature of 19.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity of 63%, wind
286 speed of 3.4 m/s and 100% cloud cover.

287

288 2.6. UAV data processing

289 2.6.1. Preprocessing

290 Raw images were aligned, orthorectified and mosaicked in the software Agisoft Metashape V2.0.0.
291 The final spatial resolution of the multispectral orthophotos was 5.4 - 5.6 cm. Reflectance values
292 were calibrated according to the recommendations of MicaSense using the spectral reflectance
293 panel for both missions, and additionally the Altum downwelling light sensor (DLS2) in cloudy
294 conditions. Conversion of digital numbers to reflectance values between 0 and 1 were achieved by
295 dividing them by 32768. The thermal band values were converted from centi-Kelvin to Celsius onto a
296 thermal orthomosaic. A Digital Surface Model was built from the dense point cloud from the
297 Structure from Motion technique, resulting in 10.9 - 11.2 cm resolution. A Canopy Height Model
298 (CHM) with the same resolution as the DSMs for the treetop identification was obtained by
299 subtracting the national Digital Elevation Model at 2 m resolution (@Lantmäteriet, 2019, Elevation
300 data, Grid 2+) from the UAV-derived DSM.

301

302 2.6.2. Tree top identification

303 We applied a previously developed framework to detect and classify healthy and dead trees from
304 drone images (Huo et al. 2023). Local maxima from smoothed green-band images were identified as
305 potential treetops, and those over 10 m in height (based on CHM) were used for analysis, with tree
306 classification performed using k-means clustering on the Green Leaf Index (See Supplementary
307 Material, Appendix 2 for details).

308

309 2.6.3. Thermal image processing

310 The thermal sensor, after pre-processing in Agisoft Metashape, provides at-sensor temperatures.
311 This means that atmospheric interactions and spatially varying thermal emissivities (due to different
312 land surface types) are not yet taken into account. Discarding these effects may yield errors in
313 estimating the land surface temperature (Heinemann et al., 2020). To correct the thermal

314 orthomosaic, we implemented the *theRmalUAV* R package (Metsu et al. 2025) to retrieve land
315 surface temperature orthomosaics. The weather conditions during the flight missions were used to
316 correct for the atmospheric interactions. Background temperature was not measured in the field
317 and, therefore, estimated using the air temperature, while either a fixed emissivity value or the NDVI
318 threshold method was chosen to estimate the thermal emissivity values. The latter method relies on
319 two NDVI thresholds with corresponding thermal emissivity values to create a gradient between two
320 classes based on vegetation cover fraction, usually bare soil and vegetation (Valor and Caselles,
321 1996). In this study we chose the lower threshold to resemble dead debarked trees and the upper
322 threshold as healthy green trees. The dead trees corresponded with an NDVI value of 0.25 and we
323 assigned a thermal emissivity of 0.9 (Zakrzewska and Kopec, 2022; Kraniotis et al., 2016). Healthy
324 trees, on the other hand, had an NDVI value of 0.9 and we used a thermal emissivity of 0.98
325 corresponding with the green foliage of coniferous species as provided in Salisbury and D’Aria
326 (1994). Besides the NDVI method, we also computed two land surface temperature orthomosaics
327 with a fixed emissivity value of 0.9 and 0.98 (the same values used in the NDVI method), as the
328 approach of using fixed emissivity values has been followed in the literature (e.g., Zakrzewska &
329 Kopec, 2022, Zakrzewska et al, 2023). In total, we generated three thermal orthomosaics per flight
330 mission, corresponding to three emissivity correction approaches.
331

332 2.6.4. Tree canopy surface temperature extraction

333 We selected all identified trees with a minimum height of 10 m above ground and that were not
334 influenced by microclimate edge effects or image distortion edge effects. In order to use similar
335 samples in both different flights, we delineated two core areas in the nature reserve, within which
336 we analysed all trees (Fig. 1b). We created a buffer with 0.5 m radius around each tree top and
337 extracted the mean temperature for each buffer/tree from the processed thermal orthomosaic.
338

339 2.7. Statistical analysis

340 2.7.1. Understory temperatures (logger data)

341 We employed multiple linear regressions to investigate the effects of bark beetle infestation
342 (quantified by the proportion of dead spruce) on daytime maximum and night-time minimum
343 temperatures, and if this effect depended on the forest type (proportion of deciduous). We included
344 interactions between the proportion of dead spruce and the proportion of deciduous trees and
345 added general forest density (*basal area*) as a covariate. We ran separate models for summer
346 average maximum and minimum temperature, as well as models for daily maximum and minimum
347 temperature for a cloudy day (31 July) and a clear day (21 July), respectively, resulting in a total of six
348 models. The cloudy and clear day were selected because we also collected drone data for these
349 days. The model structure was as follows:

350 $\text{Temperature} \sim \text{proportion dead spruce} * \text{proportion deciduous} + \text{basal area}$

351 The proportion of dead spruce was highly correlated with canopy openness (Pearson $r = 0.69$, $p <$
352 0.001), so we excluded canopy openness from the initial models. However, we ran the final models
353 again by replacing the proportion of dead spruce with canopy openness. Marginal effects plots were
354 generated with the *sjPlot* package (Lüdtke, 2023) and the *ggplot2* package (Wickham, 2016).

355 *2.7.2. Individual tree canopy temperature (UAV data)*

356 Individual average tree crown temperatures of dead and healthy trees were compared for each
357 day/scan separately using a two-sided Welch test, the non-parametric alternative to a t-test.

358 All GIS work and statistical analyses were carried out in ArcGIS (ESRI, version 10.8), QGIS version
359 3.4.7 and R 4.2.0 and 4.3.0 (R Core Team, 2023).

360

361
362

3. Results

363 3.1. Understory temperatures

364 Maximum temperatures across the 31 logger sites and two summer months were on average 21.7
365 °C, ranging from 20.6 to 23.0 °C. Summer average minimum temperatures ranged from 11.2 to 13.3
366 °C with a mean of 12.2 °C. Daily maximum temperature values (from single logger sites) ranged from
367 14.1 to 32.0 °C, whereas daily minimum temperatures ranged from 4.0 to 19.9 °C (Fig. 3).

368

369 *Fig. 3. Daily mean cloud cover (a), maximum (b) and minimum (c) temperature during July and*
370 *August 2021 measured by weather station (a) and 31 understory microclimate temperature loggers*
371 *installed at 2 m height (b, c). Highlighted are a clear sky day (21 July, 0% cloud cover) and an overcast*
372 *day (31 July, 98 % cloud cover), during which we performed UAV flights measuring canopy*
373 *temperature. We modelled summer average minimum and maximum temperature, as well as daily*
374 *minimum and maximum temperatures during these two days with contrasting cloud cover.*

375 Along an attack gradient, i.e., increasing proportion of dead trees, summer day-time maximum
 376 temperatures increased by up to 2 °C, but this warming effect was mitigated by deciduous trees (Fig.
 377 4a, Table 1). This pattern was largely driven by clear-sky days, when the effect of bark beetle
 378 infestation was particularly large on maximum temperatures (Fig. 4 c). However, even during a
 379 cloudy day with 98% cloud cover and generally lower temperatures, the temperatures were still
 380 increasing along an attack gradient, yet the mitigating effect of deciduous trees was not significant
 381 anymore (Fig. 4 b). Surprisingly, night-time minimum temperatures did not change in attacked
 382 stands (Fig. 4 d-f, Table 1). This was true both for a relatively warm cloudy night (Fig. 4 e) and for a
 383 relatively cold clear-sky night (Fig. 4 f). Replacing proportion of dead spruce with canopy openness
 384 resulted in largely similar model outcomes (Appendix 3, Table S1).

385

386 *Fig. 4. Understory temperatures at 2 m above ground as a function of bark beetle attack severity*
 387 *(expressed as proportion of dead spruce trees at each temperature logger site). a, d - Summer*
 388 *average of daily maximum (a) and minimum temperature (d). b, c, e, f - Daily maximum and*
 389 *minimum temperature during a cloudy day (b, e) and a clear day (c, f). Model summaries are given in*
 390 *Table 1 and 2. Icons from flaticon.com.*

391

392 Table 1. Results of the multiple linear regression models on maximum understory temperature data.
 393 *tmax_summer* = daily maximum temperature averaged over the entire summer (July and August
 394 2021), *max_temp_cloud* = maximum temperature during a cloudy day (31 July), *max_temp_clear* =
 395 maximum temperature during a clear day (21 July).

<i>Predictors</i>	<i>tmax_summer</i>			<i>max_temp_cloud</i>			<i>max_temp_clear</i>		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	21.52	20.55 – 22.49	<0.001	21.04	19.87 – 22.20	<0.001	22.30	20.58 – 24.02	<0.001
prop dead spruce	0.02	0.01 – 0.02	<0.001	0.01	0.01 – 0.02	<0.001	0.02	0.01 – 0.03	0.001
prop decid	0.03	0.00 – 0.06	0.036	0.02	-0.01 – 0.05	0.266	0.02	-0.03 – 0.07	0.366
basal area	-0.02	-0.05 – 0.01	0.220	-0.02	-0.06 – 0.01	0.190	-0.01	-0.06 – 0.05	0.849
prop dead spruce × prop decid	-0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.001	-0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.064	-0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.026
Observations	31			31			31		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.622 / 0.564			0.457 / 0.374			0.449 / 0.364		

396

397 Table 2. Results of the multiple linear regression models on minimum understory temperature data.
 398 *tmin_summer* = daily minimum temperature averaged over the entire summer (July and August
 399 2021), *min_temp_cloud* = minimum temperature during a cloudy day (31 July), *min_temp_clear* =
 400 minimum temperature during a clear day (21 July).

<i>Predictors</i>	<i>tmin_summer</i>			<i>min_temp_cloud</i>			<i>min_temp_clear</i>		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	11.85	10.59 – 13.10	<0.001	13.07	11.11 – 15.04	<0.001	10.81	8.73 – 12.89	<0.001
prop dead spruce	-0.01	-0.01 – 0.00	0.104	-0.00	-0.01 – 0.01	0.891	-0.01	-0.02 – 0.00	0.180
prop decid	0.00	-0.03 – 0.04	0.794	0.03	-0.03 – 0.08	0.287	0.03	-0.03 – 0.08	0.357
basal area	0.02	-0.02 – 0.06	0.358	0.02	-0.05 – 0.08	0.612	0.03	-0.03 – 0.10	0.300
prop dead spruce × prop decid	0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.573	-0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.575	-0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.838
Observations	31			31			31		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.199 / 0.075			0.084 / -0.057			0.229 / 0.110		

401

402 3.2. Canopy surface temperatures

403 Dead trees were on average warmer than living trees, by 2.6 °C (t = -67.3, df = 3503.9, p-value <
 404 0.001) and 0.7 °C (t = -33.5, df = 3903.3, p-value < 0.001) on a sunny and cloudy summer day,
 405 respectively (Fig. 5). Applying a fixed emissivity (0.98 and 0.90) to all trees resulted in similar
 406 significant differences (p-value < 0.001), but with a lower temperature contrast during the sunny day
 407 (1.3 and 1.4 °C) and slightly higher contrasts during the cloudy day (0.7 and 0.8 °C, Appendix 4, Fig.
 408 S5, Table S3).

409

410

411

412 *Fig. 5. Difference in individual tree canopy temperature of living and dead trees in the Ekeby nature*
413 *reserve during two summer days, one cloudy (left, $n = 8845$) and one sunny day (central, $n = 9687$).*
414 *Canopy temperatures were derived from UAV-derived thermal images and corrected for thermal*
415 *emissivity using the NDVI threshold method (see main text). Differences between the categories*
416 *“dead” and “alive” were significant in both cases ($p < 0.001$, two-sided Welch test). Icons from*
417 *Flaticon.com.*

418

419 4. Discussion

420 In this study, we quantified the thermal changes in bark beetle attacked forests combining high
421 temporal resolution microclimate data from a logger network with high spatial resolution thermal
422 imagery from UAV scans. To our knowledge, this study is the first that utilized both *in-situ* and *ex-*
423 *situ* approaches to study microclimate impacts of bark beetles and that investigates overstory and
424 understory temperatures together. We increased the resolution of existing knowledge on thermal
425 effects from bark beetle attacks, which were mainly based on satellite or airborne thermal imagery,
426 and we also deepened the understanding of bark beetle induced microclimate impacts by adding
427 another dimension and considering night-time temperatures. We found that bark beetles
428 significantly altered the thermal environments in forests and in the following we discuss the
429 mechanisms leading to these patterns, as well as the implications of our findings for biodiversity
430 conservation, forest management and global change monitoring and modelling.

431 Increase in understory maximum temperature

432 Understory daytime maximum temperatures increased with bark beetle attack severity. The
433 temperature increase is likely largely a result of increased canopy openness letting in more warming
434 sunlight into the understory as we found canopy openness to be correlated with proportion of dead
435 trees (Pearson $r = 0.69$, $p < 0.001$, Fig. S3). Canopy cover is one of the main drivers of forest
436 microclimate and, outside mountains, can even be the most dominant determinant of near-ground

437 maximum temperatures (De Frenne et al., 2021; Greiser et al., 2018; Haesen et al., 2021; Zellweger
438 et al., 2019). However, the warming effect was probably further increased by the drastic decrease in
439 tree transpiration and therefore drop in evaporative cooling (Anderegg et al., 2013; Chen et al.,
440 2015; Siegert et al., 2024), which is supported by our alternative models including canopy openness
441 instead of proportion of dead trees having performed less well (delta AIC = 2.23, Appendix 3, Table.
442 S2). However, as a result of reduced tree transpiration, soil moisture normally increases in bark-
443 beetle attacked stands and Edburg et al. (2012) hypothesized a successional grey stage, where
444 increased soil evaporation may (partially) compensate for the decreased tree transpiration (Fig. 4 in
445 (Edburg et al., 2012). Modelling and large-scale observations show, though, that total
446 evapotranspiration is generally decreasing (Chen et al., 2015; Maness et al., 2013). Studies that
447 monitored forest microclimate with *in-situ* loggers in temperate Norway spruce forests in central
448 Europe following bark beetle attacks also reported an increase of maximum temperature by 1.5 °C
449 (Brůna et al., 2024) and an increase of daily mean air temperatures by 1.2 °C (Kopáček et al., 2020),
450 and our study complements these numbers with estimates from the boreal forest.

451 Mitigation by deciduous broadleaf trees

452 The increase in maximum temperature was mitigated by deciduous trees, which seem to maintain
453 some degrees of forest microclimate buffering in stands, where spruce were dying and canopies
454 were opening. Deciduous broadleaf trees can have additive effects on forest microclimate buffering
455 in the boreal zone (Diaz-Calafat et al., 2023). Consequently, diversifying forests, supporting a mix of
456 tree species with a special focus on deciduous trees would not only lower the risk of one insect
457 pest/pathogen to kill an entire stand, it would also make continued microclimate buffering possible,
458 when some of the trees are killed. We therefore demonstrate yet another co-benefit of enabling the
459 (re-)establishment of deciduous trees in the managed Scandinavian forests, where spruce and pine
460 have become the dominant tree species for economic reasons (Lindbladh et al., 2014). Many
461 invertebrates, mosses, lichens and fungi species directly depend on deciduous trees as their hosts
462 and our results show that deciduous broadleaf trees are not only important for forest biodiversity as
463 food and substrate, but also are crucial drivers of microclimate buffering, which in turn affects
464 ground-dwelling species in forests (Greiser et al., 2020; Haesen et al., 2023; Koelemeijer et al., 2024;
465 Wei et al., 2024).

466 No effect on understory minimum temperatures

467 Surprisingly, understory night-time minimum temperatures were not affected by bark beetle attacks,
468 and we explain this finding by dead trees being relatively effective in preventing radiative heat loss
469 at night. Research on shelterwood has shown that a relatively low stem density is enough to
470 increase night-time temperatures and thereby reduce ground frost and frost damage on
471 regenerating tree seedlings, with increases in minimum temperature by on average 0.1 °C for each
472 basal area increment up to ca 25 m² ha⁻¹ compared to open clear cuts (Langvall & Ottosson
473 Löfvenius, 2002). Many of our heavily bark-beetle affected plots had a high stem density (minimum,
474 mean and maximum basal area of all plots was 24, 31 and 39 m² ha⁻¹, respectively) and thus fall in a
475 range, where changes in stem density do not significantly affect night-time minimum temperatures
476 (See Fig. 5 in Langvall & Ottosson Löfvenius, 2002). Moreover, buffering of night-time temperatures
477 is not directly dependent on living transpiring tissues, therefore even standing deadwood can
478 function as a buffer for low temperature extremes. Considering the asymmetry in temperature
479 effects on day- and night-time temperatures caused by bark beetles, we conclude that infested
480 stands are not only characterized by novel light regimes (De Frenne, 2024) but also by novel

481 microclimate regimes. When dead trees still buffer the understory against cold night-time
482 temperature, opposed to conditions on an open clearcut, (Greiser et al., 2018; Starck et al., 2025),
483 we conclude that salvage logging of trees in old attack stands may be counterproductive in areas
484 where sensitive understory diversity and regenerating trees are dependent on this buffering
485 function. Additionally, standing and sun-exposed deadwood is a rare resource in managed boreal
486 forests (Jonsson et al., 2016) and is important habitat to many threatened saproxylic insects and
487 fungi with almost one quarter of all forest species in the Nordic countries depending on dead trees
488 (Esseen et al., 1997; Plath & Fischer, 2024; Siitonen, 2001). Taken together, whenever possible,
489 attacked stands may be left for natural succession as salvage logging does not only remove valuable
490 substrate but also removes a protective layer buffering against cold extreme temperatures.

491 **Warmer canopy surface temperatures**

492 Tree canopies of dead trees were on average 0.7 - 2.6 °C warmer than living trees, which is in line
493 with previous remote sensing research demonstrating that bark beetle attacks lead to canopy
494 warming (Hais & Kučera, 2008; Junttila et al., 2017; Kozhoridze et al., 2023; Maness et al., 2013;
495 Zakrzewska et al., 2023). The results from our study were very consistent with e.g., Zakrzewska &
496 Kopeć (2022), although our study used multispectral images to classify healthy and dead trees,
497 which led to more accurate classification and more robust analysis of the crown surface
498 temperature. In fact, like several other studies, Zakrzewska & Kopeć (2022) used thermal imagery to
499 classify healthy and dead trees, whereas we used other spectra to classify trees and then quantify
500 their temperature differences.

501 The absolute temperature differences are difficult to compare across studies, as thermal sensors are
502 not always calibrated with ground measurements, and because different emissivity corrections were
503 applied. Thus, absolute temperature values should be interpreted with care. Applying a constant
504 emissivity, as done by Junttila et al. (2017) and Zakrzewska & Kopeć (2022), yielded smaller
505 temperature differences than applying a gradual emissivity correction depending on NDVI values,
506 which we did and believe is the more correct approach (Heinemann et al., 2020). However, in order
507 to derive more accurate canopy surface temperature estimates from UAV-borne thermal imagery,
508 more research is needed to quantify the emissivity of different tree species and spruce trees in
509 different attack stages. Another limitation arises from the fact that a UAV image represents only one
510 snapshot in time, complicating the comparison with other studies. Extensive and repeated sampling
511 is needed here to arrive at a comprehensive understanding of the thermal properties of healthy,
512 stressed and dead trees. Smigaj et al. (2023) summarizes thermal responses as a result of tree stress
513 and mortality and explains temperature increases mainly as a consequence of decreases in tree
514 transpiration and thus decreases of evaporative cooling. As tree transpiration follows solar radiation
515 but also atmospheric vapour pressure deficit and soil water content, differences in canopy
516 temperature are expected even within one day (Smigaj et al., 2023). Interestingly, a warming effect
517 due to stress was also reported for night-time temperatures of urban trees (Zakrzewska et al., 2023),
518 though the temperature differences relative to healthy trees were not as big as during the day.
519 Extending UAV-borne thermal imagery to also include night-time conditions is desirable to get a
520 more complete picture of the thermal changes after forest disturbances in general and bark beetle
521 attacks in particular.

522 Effect of weather conditions

523 Weather conditions mediated the effect bark beetle attacks had on canopy surface and understory
524 air temperature. Clear skies generally enhanced the thermal signature of bark beetles, which was
525 also reported by Smigaj et al. (2023), who found accentuated differences between healthy and
526 stressed trees during weather conditions favouring increased transpiration rates, for instance, when
527 vapour pressure deficit is high (Flo et al., 2022). This was also the most likely explanation for Junttila
528 et al. (2017) finding relatively small effects of tree health on canopy temperature of boreal forests in
529 Finland (3 °C air temperature, and 80% RH). We are currently observing changing trends in amount
530 and type of clouds in Europe (Devasthale et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023) driven by decreasing aerosol
531 loads (i.e., fewer condensation nuclei) and increasing vapour pressure deficit (i.e., fewer
532 condensation events). We can therefore conclude that conditions favouring the local-scale
533 temperature differences in forests, caused by bark-beetle induced variations in evapotranspiration
534 or shading, are therefore potentially increasing. Further studies using UAV-borne thermal surveys
535 should carefully take into account weather conditions and, whenever possible, repeat surveys under
536 different conditions (Smigaj et al., 2023). On a technical note, our findings also imply that thermal
537 imagery for the purpose of detecting drought-stressed or infested trees may be more successful in
538 warm, dry and cloud-free conditions (Smigaj et al., 2019, 2023).

539 Feedbacks to regional weather and climate

540 By documenting a warming effect on summer maximum temperatures in forest understories and
541 canopies, our study contributes to the growing body of literature on atmosphere-biosphere
542 feedbacks, where ecological impacts of climate change (drought-stressed trees, bark beetle
543 infestations) lead to accelerated local climate change (understory warming due to more open
544 canopy) and feed back to regional climate change. We demonstrate how plants (here: trees) are not
545 only affected by climate but also modify local climate (Royer et al., 2011). Studies on larger-scale
546 bark beetle outbreaks and canopy dieback in temperate Europe and in the US have demonstrated
547 this change in energy and moisture balance at the regional level (Hais & Kučera, 2008; Maness et al.,
548 2013). With our study on tree-level changes in temperature, we confirm these findings. However, in
549 a next step more research is needed to upscale patchy and variable canopy dieback (as in our study
550 area) to regional climatic changes (Maness et al., 2013). Ultimately, these positive feedback
551 mechanisms that lead to locally and regionally warmer and drier climate will boost bark-beetle
552 outbreaks even further (Huang et al., 2020; Kozhoridze et al., 2023; Netherer et al., 2024),
553 potentially increasing large-scale forest dieback even in the cold-humid boreal zone.
554

555 Conclusions

556 Globally, forests of the boreal biome experience the fastest rate of climate warming (IPCC, 2013;
557 Price et al., 2013) and are currently under threat from multiple stressors and disturbances, such as
558 droughts, megafires, harvesting, wind through, new pathogens and insect pest outbreaks. Our study
559 was one of the first that quantified the thermal consequences of bark beetle disturbances in the
560 overstory and understory of boreal forests as one of the mechanisms leading to biosphere-
561 atmosphere feedbacks and to increased local warming. Characterizing and considering these novel
562 microclimate regimes emerging in disturbed forests helps in informing decision makers on how to
563 manage affected forests, whether to salvage-log or not, and how to support forest regeneration and
564 biodiversity in forests reliant on specific microclimates. Our results support growing calls to diversify

565 (Sommerfeld et al., 2021) and “de-sprucify” Scandinavian managed forests (Lindbladh et al., 2014) to
566 increase forest resilience and secure ecosystem functions such as microclimate buffering. Further
567 research on climatic consequences of forest canopy disturbances should be carried out at all scales,
568 at the tree and stand scale to be able to give regional and concrete management advice and at
569 landscape scale to be able to include these feedbacks into regional and global land surface models.
570 As true ecosystem engineers, bark beetles alter not only microclimate but also snow accumulation
571 and melt, water supply, water quality, carbon storage and nutrient cycling in forests (Anderegg et al.,
572 2013; Edburg et al., 2012). Understanding all these interlinked effects and how they change in time
573 and along successional stages and across geographical gradients is therefore important to manage
574 forest and water resources as well as ecosystem functioning.

575 Acknowledgement

576

577 This work was funded by the Oscar and Lilli Lamm Foundation [project grant to PL], the Bolin Centre
578 for Climate Research [project grant to CG, PL, IB], the Swedish Research Council Formas [project
579 grant 2021-01993 to CG; project grant 2024-00404 to LH], Internal Funds of KU Leuven [project grant
580 C14/22/067 to KVM and CM].

581 We would like to thank Teo Jernkvist, Lucas McMaster, Isak Sundström for help with data collection
582 and processing.

583

584 Data availability statement

585

586 Data and script underlying this study are available at the Figshare database under the following link
587 [link made available upon manuscript acceptance]. Private link for review:

588 <https://figshare.com/s/d23c6b596faa9dc485b4>

589

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881 **Figure and table captions**

882

883

884 *Table 1. Results of the multiple linear regression models on maximum understory temperature data.*
885 *tmax_summer = daily maximum temperature averaged over the entire summer (July and August*
886 *2021), max_temp_cloud = maximum temperature during a cloudy day (31 July), max_temp_clear =*
887 *maximum temperature during a clear day (21 July).*

888

889 *Table 2. Results of the multiple linear regression models on minimum understory temperature data.*
890 *tmin_summer = daily minimum temperature averaged over the entire summer (July and August*
891 *2021), min_temp_cloud = minimum temperature during a cloudy day (31 July), min_temp_clear =*
892 *minimum temperature during a clear day (21 July).*

893

894 *Fig. 1. a) Schematic overview of our two approaches to study b) understory temperature differences*
895 *along an attack gradient, and c) canopy surface temperature differences between living and dead*
896 *trees. The study area is situated in Södermanland county, Sweden (b), where we installed 31 loggers*
897 *across five nature reserves. In one of the reserves (Ekeby), we also collected UAV-borne thermal*
898 *imagery to estimate canopy surface temperature (c). The two core areas used for analyses of canopy*
899 *surface temperature are delineated in blue in the orthophoto in panel b).*

900

901 *Fig. 2. Distribution of summer-averaged daily understory maximum and minimum temperature,*
902 *elevation, proportion of dead spruce trees, proportion of deciduous trees and canopy openness of 31*
903 *microclimate logger sites, obtained during the growing season 2021. Proportion of dead and*
904 *deciduous trees is based on on-site basal area measurements. See Table S1 for site-specific features.*

905

906 *Fig. 3. Daily mean cloud cover (a), maximum (b) and minimum (c) temperature during July and*
907 *August 2021 measured by weather station (a) and 31 understory microclimate temperature loggers*
908 *installed at 2 m height (b, c). Highlighted are a clear sky day (21 July, 0% cloud cover) and an overcast*
909 *day (31 July, 98 % cloud cover), during which we performed UAV flights measuring canopy*
910 *temperature. We modelled summer average minimum and maximum temperature, as well as daily*
911 *minimum and maximum temperatures during these two days with contrasting cloud cover.*

912

913 *Fig. 4. Understory temperatures at 2 m above ground as a function of bark beetle attack severity*
914 *(expressed as proportion of dead spruce trees at each temperature logger site). a, d - Summer*
915 *average of daily maximum (a) and minimum temperature (d). b, c, e, f - Daily maximum and*
916 *minimum temperature during a cloudy day (b, e) and a clear day (c, f). Model summaries are given in*
917 *Table 1 and 2. Icons from flaticon.com.*

918

919 *Fig. 5. Difference in individual tree canopy temperature of living and dead trees in the Ekeby nature*
920 *reserve during two summer days, one cloudy (left, n = 8845) and one sunny day (central, n = 9687).*
921 *Canopy temperatures were derived from UAV-derived thermal images and corrected for thermal*
922 *emissivity using the NDVI threshold method (see main text). Differences between the categories*
923 *“dead” and “alive” were significant in both cases ($p < 0.001$, two-sided Welch test). Icons from*
924 *Flaticon.com.*

925